

Investigations on the Formation of Cerium(III) Thiotungstates

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Compounds formed by the interaction of cerous nitrate with different sodium thiotungstates ($\text{Na}_2\text{S.WS}_3$, $3\text{Na}_2.4\text{WS}_3$, $\text{Na}_2\text{S.2WS}_3$ and $\text{Na}_2\text{S.4WS}_3$) have been investigated by pH and conductometric titrations at different pH ranges. Well-defined breaks in the titration curves provide cogent evidence for the formation and precipitation of two cerous thiotungstates having molecular formulae, $\text{Ce}_2\text{S}_3.3\text{WS}_3$ and $\text{Ce}_2\text{S}_3.4\text{WS}_3$ around pH 7.7 and 7.0, respectively. Titrations of the cerium salt with $\text{Na}_2\text{S.2WS}_3$ and $\text{Na}_2\text{S.4WS}_3$ failed to provide any dependable results. The course of the reactions was also followed by means of analytical method which supports the results obtained by the electrometric study.

An outstanding characteristic of the tungstates and thiotungstates is their strong tendency to form condensed complex ions in solution, as revealed by the observations of Jander and Jahr¹, from these, polytungstates crystallise, depending on the hydrogen ion concentration which plays an important role in the aggregation process. The existence of polytungstates is usually attributed to combination with the corresponding acids as if these were separate chemical individuals. This led the previous workers to believe that similar salts of heavy metals might be precipitated as a result of metathesis². Britton and German³, however, contended that the corresponding salts of heavy metals were not precipitated by the interaction of respective salts and different alkali tungstates.

The difficulties associated with analytical work and the absence of any decisive views on the composition of thiotungstates interested the author in the investigation of their synthesis and properties. In earlier publications^{4,5}, the results on the polymerisation of thiotungstate anions (WS_4)²⁻, and the formation and composition of Hg^{2+} and Zn^{2+} thiotungstates have been reported. In view of the interesting results obtained, it was considered worthwhile to extend similar investigations on the reaction between Ce^{3+} and alkali thiotungstates by means of pH and conductometric titrations, for which no reference could be traced in the literature.

Experimental

Anal. reagents, tungstic acid, cerous nitrate, sodium sulphide, ammonium sulphide and hydrochloric acid were used and their solutions were prepared in air-free conductivity water. The

solution of sodium thiotungstate was prepared⁴ by digesting analysed sample of tungsten trisulphide in sodium sulphide solution of required strength.

pH measurements were carried out on a Metrohm pH meter using Schott Geräte glass combination electrode. The conductance of the solutions were measured by employing a Metrohm conductometer. 40 ml of either solution was taken in the cell each time. Using different concentrations of the reactants, a series of pH and conductometric titrations were performed both by direct and reverse methods in aqueous as well as in aqueous alcoholic media. The titration cell was kept at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

The solution of sodium thiotungstate, $\text{Na}_2\text{S.WS}_3$, was prepared by digesting WS_3 in Na_2S solution in equimolar ratio.

The other sodium thiotungstates were prepared by progressive additions of dilute HCl to boiling solution of $\text{Na}_2\text{S.WS}_3$ in the molecular ratio 1 : 2, 1 : 1 and 3 : 2, and the corresponding compounds formed⁴ were

Na₂S.WS₃ titrations: It is clear from Fig. 1. (curve 1) that in direct titrations when cerous nitrate solution was added from microburette to $\text{Na}_2\text{S.WS}_3$ solution in the cell, the pH of the latter shows

a gradual decrease with a marked downward jump in pH at the stoichiometric end-point, which corresponds to the formation and precipitation of cerous thiotungstate, $Ce_2S_3 \cdot 3WS_3$. In case of inverse titrations (Fig. 1, curve 2), when $Na_2S \cdot WS_3$ solution is used as titrant, the pH of cerous nitrate solution gradually increases till a sharp rise in pH is obtained indicating the end-point, where the molecular ratio of $Ce^{3+} : WS_4^{2-}$ is 2 : 3, suggesting the formation of $Ce_2S_3 \cdot 3WS_3$ according to the equation,

Fig. 1. Curves 1 and 3: ml of $M/10$ $Ce(NO_3)_3$ added to 40 ml of $M/130$ $Na_2S \cdot WS_3$; curves 2 and 4: ml of $M/10$ $Na_2S \cdot WS_3$ added to 40 ml of $M/300$ $Ce(NO_3)_3$.

Employing similar concentrations of cerous nitrate and $Na_2S \cdot WS_3$ solutions a series of direct and reverse curves (Fig. 1, curves 3 and 4) conductometric titrations were performed. The titration curves yield well-defined breaks at the stoichiometric end-points corresponding to the formation of the same compound, $Ce_2S_3 \cdot 3WS_3$.

$3Na_2S \cdot 4WS_3$ titrations: The solution of $3Na_2S \cdot 4WS_3$ was prepared as described earlier. The pH (Fig. 2, curves 1 and 2) and the conductometric (Fig. 2, curves 3 and 4) titrations provide well-defined breaks and inflections at the molecular ratio of $Ce^{3+} : WS_4^{2-}$ as 2 : 1, suggesting the

Fig. 2. Curves 1 and 3: ml of $M/10$ $Ce(NO_3)_3$ added to 40 ml of $M/400$ $3Na_2S \cdot 4WS_3$; curves 2 and 4: ml of $M/40$ $3Na_2S \cdot 4WS_3$ added to 40 ml of $M/400$ $Ce(NO_3)_3$.

formation of $Ce_2S_3 \cdot 4WS_3$ in the vicinity of pH 7.0. The reaction can be represented by the following equation

The reactions of cerous nitrate with $Na_2S \cdot 2WS_3$ and $Na_2S \cdot 4WS_3$ have also been studied by pH and conductometric titrations but the curves do not exhibit any appreciable inflections.

It is noted that after each addition of the titrant, it takes a little time for the pH and conductance values to become steady. A thorough stirring in the neighbourhood of the equivalence point has a favourable effect. Each titration takes about half an hour for completion. The titration curves are regular in shape and the results are reproducible and accurate. The presence of ethanol (20%) increased the magnitude of the jump in the titration curves as a consequence of the decrease in solubility of the precipitates formed.

Analytical study: Analytical investigations were also carried out with a view to substantiate the electrometric results. The cerium thiotungstates were prepared by mixing stoichiometric amounts of cerous nitrate and different sodium thiotungstates. The precipitate obtained in each case was washed several times with 10% ethanolic water and dried completely by keeping it in a vacuum desiccator for 40 h. A known amount of

TABLE 1—SUMMARY OF RESULTS OF ELECTROMETRIC TITRATIONS

Volume of titre solution taken in the cell = 40 ml

Molarity of solutions		Equivalence points (ml)			Formula supported		
		Calcd.	Observed pH	from Cond.			
Ce(NO ₃) ₃	Na ₂ S.WS ₃	Direct titrations. Fig. 1, curves 1 and 3.			Ce ₂ S ₃ .3WS ₃		
	M/10	M/130	2.05	2.05		2.10	
	M/20	M/250	2.13	2.15		2.15	
	M/30	M/400	2.00	2.00	2.00	Ce ₂ S ₃ .3WS ₃	
	Reverse titrations. Fig. 1, curves 2 and 4			2.00	2.00		
	M/300	M/10	1.85	1.85	1.80		
	M/650	M/20	1.80	1.80	1.80		
	M/1000	M/30	2.00	2.00	2.00		
	Ce(NO ₃) ₃	3Na ₂ S.4WS ₃	Direct titrations, Fig. 2, curves 1 and 3				Ce ₂ S ₃ .4WS ₃
		M/10	M/400	2.00	2.00		
M/20		M/850	1.90	1.90	1.95		
M/30		M/1100	2.18	2.20	2.20	Ce ₂ S ₃ .4WS ₃	
Reverse titrations. Fig. 2, curves 2 and 4			2.00	2.00			
M/400		M/40	2.40	2.40	2.40		
M/500		M/60	2.13	2.10	2.10		
M/750		M/80	2.13	2.10	2.10		

each (2 g) was treated with concentrated HNO₃ (15 ml) and then digested to dryness on a steam bath. The acid treatment was repeated again. The dry residue was then heated with 5N NaOH solution (30 ml) to separate cerium from tungsten. The tungsten was estimated as oxinate⁶ and cerium volumetrically⁶. The sulphur content in different cerium thiotungstates was determined gravimetrically by the wet process⁶. From the proportions of cerium, tungsten and sulphur in the compounds thus obtained, their compositions were established, which were found to be the same as obtained by electrometric methods.

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